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Enhancing group work learning with the Individual Peer Assessed Contribution (IPAC)

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ABSTRACT

In 'Are Universities Redundant', Arvanitakis and Hornsby (2015) suggest that global, technological and scientific changes are driving change of curriculum design in University that curriculum design needs to embed the concept of the 'Citizen Scholar' which promote scholarship and *inculcate a set of skills and cultural practices that educate students beyond their disciplinary knowledge*. How to Change the World is a two-week scenario for second year engineering undergraduates that emphasises engineering's potential as a vehicle for positive change. This paper attempts to explore the effectiveness of embedding peer assessment in the Programme to assist graduates reflecting on across a range of proficiencies and attributes that are essential for the challenges of tomorrow. IPAC (Individual Peer Assessed Contribution) is developed and led by Dr Pilaras Garcia Souto as a pedagogical tool and a digital tool to train graduates to give constructive criticism, meaningful and professional feedback to each other in group work assessment. This peer assessment was also designed to improve the fairness and transparency of group work assessment across these proficiency clusters.

The quantitative data confirmed that overall student engagement was improved. It suggested that students within their group seem to understand better about their roles and responsibilities; the proficiency to deliver the expected assessment outcomes; and the value of their individual contribution to group work. Although the overall assessment grades were not comparable to suggest whether graduates achieve higher learning levels, this paper suggested that graduates were motivated to learn in a group work with peer assessment format.

INTRODUCTION

Our world is now much better connected than ever before. Technological enhancements in computing science enable people to work seamlessly regardless of geographic, time and language barriers. Complex challenges, such as climate change, global health, sustainable energy and rapid urbanisation, have significant global impacts on social, economic, educational and cultural levels. The global, technological and scientific changes are driving structural change at a global level affecting the way we live, learn and work. University graduates not only require having the knowledge competencies, but they are also expected to equip a range proficiency to enable them to deal with complex global challenges in fast changing environment. This paper aims to use a two-weeks intensive inter-engineering

programme entitled “How to Change the World” delivered by the Department of Science, Technology, Engineering and Public Policy in the University College of London (UCL) for a cohort of six hundred and sixty- seven students as a case study to explore the effectiveness of using an online peers' assessment within a problem-based learning approach to enhance student engagement and tackle issues associated with group work. The paper will draw qualitative data from two separate evaluations and the programme teaching log to inform the impacts and further development.

1 THE PADAGOGY

1.1 The concept of “Citizen Scholar”

Arvanitakis and Hornsby (2015) argue that universities simply offer education around disciplinary content alone is no longer adequate to address the needs of the 21st century graduate. Universities need to future-proof themselves by focus on a new set of ‘Graduate Proficiencies’. Particularly important to this is the concept of the ‘Citizen Scholar’ in which it is the role of a university to promote scholarship and inculcate a set of skills and cultural practices that educate students beyond their disciplinary knowledge.

As a part of the Citizen Scholar concept, the writers identify distinct groups of ‘proficiency clusters’ as a broader categorisation of proficiencies and attributes that are essential for preparing students for the challenges of tomorrow.

These proficiency clusters are as follows;

Cluster 1: Creativity and Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Critical Thinking · Problem Solving · Reflexivity · Entrepreneurship · Being Process Driven · Systems thinking
Cluster 2: Resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Adaptability · Mistakability/ Perseverance
Cluster 3: Working Across Teams and Across Experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Interdisciplinary · Cross-cultural understanding · Developing new literacies · Internationalisation · Inclusivity
Cluster 4: Design Thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · People-centred thinking · Aesthetics · Ethical Leadership

These proficiency and attributes are especially important in the case of engineering programmes in UCL. We ask our graduates constantly to transcend their own particular disciplines and identify in particular how they can mobilise science, technologies and engineering through the use of diplomacy and leadership to

practically navigate stakeholder concerns, lead interdisciplinary teams, and can communicate and engage with wide range of audiences through a variety of media. Two teaching and learning approaches are adopted to enable graduates to learn and apply these proficiencies: problem-based learning and peer assessment.

1.2 Choosing the right teaching and learning approaches

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is an approach that put student as the centre of learning in which a problem needs to be solved. Students learn both new knowledge about the subject domain as well as problem-solving skills when they learn individually. But when they work in groups with their peers and use their prerequisite knowledge to define the problems, acquire new knowledge to design innovative solutions; this process fosters further development of communication, collaboration, and self-directed learning skills (Hmelo-Silver, 2004). These anticipated learning outcomes match the concept of 'Citizen Scholar' and the PBL is also proven approach that works well with peer assessment.

Peer assessment is defined as an arrangement in which individuals consider the amount, level, value, worth, quality, or success of the products or outcomes of learning of peers of similar status (Topp, 2009). Studies have informed that peer assessment is an effective learning approach to promote the development of teamwork and other professional skills in undergraduate students. It fosters the ability to critically evaluate their own learning and in helping students to develop a sense of ownership of their learning (Boud, 2007; Sivan, 2000). Although PBL and peer assessment offer great benefits to student's learning, there are challenges in deploying them in group work learning.

The most common issue within group work is that some students present in the learning activities and pretend to be active but let others do the actual work. Group work assessment tend to give a collective mark equally to each group member. For student, these so-called "free riders" quite often affect the group dynamic: they demotivate others who would feel unfair as these "free rider" would receive the same mark as them. Other common issues within group work are absence of team leadership, poor communication, lack of participation and inability to resolve conflict etc. For teacher: it is difficult to intervene without any substantial evidence. Peer assessment is recognized as a good approach to tackle some of these student group work issues: students understand the marking criteria and in return understand better of how to achieve meeting the learning the objectives as a group by recognizing their individual roles and responsibilities. The feedback from the peers also provide teacher an insight of how well each group work. Still students can co-op themselves by agreeing on giving each other the same mark or game-on individual(s) within the group. There is also an administrative burden when conducting peer assessment manually. What it shows is that peer assessment method does not eliminate every issue associated with group work but the benefits to student's learning are outweigh the potential drawbacks. Provided Together with an online peer assessment tool, teachers could administrate the process more effectively.

2 METHODOLOGY

This paper uses UCL How to Change the World with a cohort of 676 second-year engineering students as a case study to examine the effectiveness of using peer assessment to enhance student engagement and address group work associated issues when it is deployed in problem-based learning. Evidence will be drawn from feedback from two separate evaluations and the programme teaching log.

2.1 How to Change the World

The 'How to Change the World' (HtCTW) is designed with the concepts of 'Citizen Scholar' and a pedagogy that shift away from contents to a more problem-based learning approach. Throughout the UCL engineering degrees, students are taught the key technical skills they need to be leaders in their field. HtCtW aims to teach students the skills they need to apply this knowledge to specific real-world problems in a meaningful way.

In this two-weeks intensive programme (9 days teaching/ workshop facilitation), students are grouped in teams and work on open-ended problems, considering social and cultural contexts, and the different ways business and governments are motivated to engage with these changes. Students work in their teams and they are required to provide a design solution to a specific challenge. These challenge briefs are created in partnership with external experts, from policy, industry and the third sector and they are based on the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) that relate to poverty, inequality, climate, environmental degradation, prosperity and peace and justice.

One of the primary objectives of this programme is to promote an interdisciplinary approach to some of these world's big challenges. Each team is designed to consist of students from 7 different departments in UCL Engineering, ranging from Mechanical Engineering to Chemical Engineering and School of Management. The aim of this is to get students from several disciplines to create unique solutions to challenging issues. Students are encouraged to allocate team roles. For example, students from the School of Management may want to take on business and implementation plans, whereas engineers may want to take on technical aspects of design, and computer scientists equip the project with smart additions.

The programme is delivered through facilitated workshops in which students explore the social, political, and economic dimensions relating to their designated challenge. They were guided to use frameworks that enabled them to narrow the scope and produce innovative design concepts, whilst benefiting from feedback and input from external partners. On the final day, each team displayed their work at an Innovation Showcase and pitch their concepts to a panel of experts.

On Day One after the initial plenary session, students join their Challenge Cohort, meet the other students in their team and dive in the process to develop their design. From Day Two to Three, students have to complete their draft design brief (before the end of Week 1). On Day Five student will finalise their design brief after discussion with expertise; develop the design concept and produce presentation materials on Day Six and Seven; and Day Eight to pitch the concept to a panel of experts and Day Nine students showcase their works to their peers.

The programme is designed to be intensive with a level of uncertainty to reflect on the real-world environment: the programme consists of nine days in total; students are put in an interdisciplinary team that they never work with each other before; and the challenge briefs are complex to address.

To meet the learning outcomes successfully, students need to communicate across interdisciplinary; work in teams to gain an understanding of the complexity and challenges of the interconnected world; gain a strong sense of social, ethical and political responsibility. Students need to apply skills like teamwork, leadership and problem solving through innovation and entrepreneurship. Within their teams, students need to make every effort to include the expertise of all team members in the final design solution.

In previous years HtCtW experienced problems of student’s engagement that some students did not turn up after the first week and some groups were dismantled due to team dysfunction. Programme evaluation revealed that they were partly caused by the timing of the programme but mainly issues of working in a team. All students were required to attend the programme right after they finished their final examinations and students generally felt fatigue at this point. To address the issues of student working in a team such as “free rider”, a probation method was used

when teams find that a member was not contributing: they could put this person on probation, which gave them 24 hours to re-engage with the group work. The team members would take a vote again on whether this person had shown that they are willing to contribute. If the team voted that this person was still disengaged, then steps would be taken by staff to get to the root of the problem. If the person on probation was found not to have engaged, then they would be awarded zero for the current assignment that the team were working towards and the team would continue without them.

Our experience showed that this probation process worked well on student complete disengagement, but it was less effective for those who intended to contribute to the minimal. The process did not allow staff to give students a fairer grade on the individual: it penalised the members who did not contribute but it did not reward those who contribute more than the others. It was perceived by students as a threat to trigger negative criticisms from team members towards the individual(s) rather than a motivational factor to encourage every team member to make positive contributions.

It was not easy for any team or staff to determine who contribute proportionally less than others during the programme as each member could not contribute equally at every single stage due to the nature of tasks and their subject disciplines.

The stake was high for any team who triggered the probation process because it would certainly create an uncomfortable atmosphere afterwards regardless of the actual outcome and such team might also lose such member(s) for the rest of the design process.

The programme needs to adopt an approach to work for both students and staff. It would allow students to make positive feedback to motivate their peers for good contribution and equally to make constructive feedback to reflect their peers who should make more contribution. Such approach would also allow staff to understand the group dynamic during the course of the team work; provide them scopes to try to address the issues; and to provide student grades that reflect on their contribution to the group work.

2.2 IPAC

To address this problem, IPAC (Individual Peer Assessed Contribution of group work) is adopted. This peer assessment method has been developed by Pilar Garcia Souto, Omer Mirza and Arjun Khurana to assess group work where an element of 'individual peer assessed contribution' is combined with the group mark to provide individual marks. It is used to address concern about the fairness of group assessment, which can consequently damage the student's experience during learning. The aim of this methodology is to provide student's with an individual mark that is based on their contribution, rather than all members getting the same group mark.

The group complete the project as designed and receive a mark for this work. An assessment of each member's contribution can be completed as many times as required, and these marks will be used to calculate scores by an online tool specifically developed for IPAC. These two marks will then be combined to give each member their own grade, reflecting not only the final piece of assessed work but also how she or he functioned in the group over the whole project.

This online IPAC tool collects the ratings and comments completed by the students via an online questionnaire within Moodle, the University's Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), and it generates scores through a variety of methods including normalisation and bias correction. This method first corrects the students' ratings by examining the degree of leniency of each student (the bias). If a student gives out more ratings than the average received rating in the group, then their outgoing ratings will be scaled down. The opposite is true for students who are overly generous; their outgoing ratings will be scaled up. Following this, the bias corrected ratings are then used to create individual contribution factors and from there calculate the final scores for students. Two files are generated by the tool to enable staff to see the individual scores and comments; and upload the file to VLE for students to view.

It will save the two output files: 'Student_contribution_summary.csv' and 'Scores_and_Comments.csv'.
 The 'student contributions summary' file contains the following information:

- Organized raw data per group and per criteria element
- Averages and SD associated to each student and criteria element
- Organized comments given to each student by their peers
- Summary per student of the average and standard deviation value obtained for each criteria, after all the normalization and bias correction methods have been applied (when required by the user in the settings window)
- Final IPAC values per student, and normalised values if included in the method. (at the far right end)

Group	Student	Assessment Criterion 1					Assessment Criterion 2					Assessment Criterion 3								
		Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Student 5	Average	Standard Deviation	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Student 5	Average	Standard Deviation	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Student 5
Group 1	Student 1	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.6000	0.5477	6.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.8000	0.4472	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Student 2	5.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	6.0	5.4000	0.5477	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	6.0	5.6000	0.5477	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	4.0
	Student 3	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0000	0.0000	6.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	6.0	5.4000	0.5477	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Student 4	4.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	6.0	5.4000	0.8944	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	6.0	5.8000	0.4472	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0
	Student 5	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0000	0.0000	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0000	0.0000	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0
Group 2	Student 1	6.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.8000	0.4472	6.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.8000	0.4472	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Student 2	2.0	4.0	1.0	6.0	4.0	3.4000	1.9494	2.0	5.0	2.0	6.0	5.0	4.0000	1.8708	2.0	5.0	2.0	2.0	6.0
	Student 3	6.0	4.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.4000	0.8944	6.0	4.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.4000	0.8944	6.0	4.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Student 4	6.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.8000	0.4472	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.8000	0.4472	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Student 5	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	5.0	4.6000	1.1402	5.0	4.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.2000	0.8367	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
Group 3	Student 1	0.0	5.0	3.0	0.0	3.0	3.6667	1.1547	0.0	6.0	4.0	0.0	6.0	5.3333	1.1547	0.0	6.0	3.0	0.0	0.0
	Student 2	0.0	6.0	5.0	0.0	6.0	5.6667	0.5774	0.0	5.0	6.0	0.0	6.0	5.6667	0.5774	0.0	5.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
	Student 3	0.0	5.0	6.0	0.0	6.0	5.6667	0.5774	0.0	5.0	5.0	0.0	6.0	5.3333	0.5774	0.0	6.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
	Student 4	0.0	6.0	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0000	0.0000	0.0	6.0	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0000	0.0000	0.0	5.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
	Student 5	0.0	5.0	6.0	0.0	6.0	5.6667	0.5774	0.0	5.0	6.0	0.0	6.0	5.6667	0.5774	0.0	6.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
Group 4	Student 1	4.0	0.0	5.0	6.0		5.0000	1.0000	4.0	0.0	6.0	6.0		5.3333	1.1547	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Student 2	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0		6.0000	0.0000	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0		6.0000	0.0000	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Student 3	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0		6.0000	0.0000	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0		6.0000	0.0000	6.0	0.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Student 4	6.0	0.0	2.0	6.0		4.6667	2.3094	6.0	0.0	2.0	6.0		4.6667	2.3094	6.0	0.0	1.0	6.0	6.0
Group 5	Student 1	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0		6.0000	0.0000	6.0	5.0	6.0	5.0		5.5000	0.5774	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Student 2	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0		5.7500	0.5000	6.0	4.0	6.0	5.0		5.2500	0.9574	6.0	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.0

Scores and Comments File
 The 'scores and comments' file summaries the information in the 'student contributions summary' file.
 For each student, their average IPAC score for each question and overall is displayed, as well as each comment they received. Any flagged words are also highlighted here.
 This is the document that can be used to give feedback to the students.

Name	Email Address	IPAC Score	C1 Average	C2 Average	C3 Average	C4 Average	C5 Average	C6 Average	Overall
Marie		0.9867	5.75	5.75	5.00	5.75	5.25	5.00	5.42
Blaise		0.9674	5.25	5.50	5.00	5.50	5.25	5.00	5.25
Albert		0.9717	5.00	5.50	5.50	5.25	5.25	5.25	5.29

The IPAC tool also offer teachers to moderate the scores before they are released to students, for example a student is rated as absent or having contributed very little to the group, yet they have peer assessed the other members in their team. During the moderation process, teacher can use the ratings and feedback from the group and discuss specific issues with students before deciding the final grades.

In 2018 HtCtW, a cohort of 662 were grouped in 130 teams and all students were informed about IPAC both in writing in the programme handbook and at the very first taught session of the programme about this method.

The IPAC method was incorporated into the activity assessment which was used as formative tool in the first week – to identify problems – and as a summative tool in the second week – for the actual assessment marks. All students were required to take part these two rounds of the assessments. The first round of IPAC is designed to let students know how their peers rate their contributions to the team and adjust their efforts if necessary. The outcomes of it also inform teaching staff any signs of issue within the group and allow them to address such issues before they escalate further.

Students were informed that they would give and receive the scores and meaningful and individual feedback from and to their peers. They were guided on how they would rate and give feedback to their peers across five areas (**communication** and **sharing of disciplinary** knowledge; **team-working** skills; **quality** of research and application of technical and professional skills; **time** and

effort contributed throughout the project; **overall value** to the team's success) using 5 levels of marking criteria (Poor, Unsatisfactory, Satisfactory, Good, and Excellent). Although marks and feedback were anonymised, they were required to provide justification on their ratings and be constructive.

2.3 Impacts of introduced peer assessment

The completion rate for both IPAC assessments are as below:

Cohort	1st IPAC %	2nd IPAC %
C1	91	78
C2	93	78
E1	89	73
E2	88	55
M1	95	72
M2	89	59
T1	91	76
T2	94	72
W1	94	63
W2	88	74
Overall	91	70

The participation rate of the first IPAC formative assessment was 91%. Staff were very motivated by the high level of student's participation and they found the process was very useful because students provided them different insights about their group dynamic. Despite no report from staff about taking immediate action to any of the students who perceived to be less engage with the team, staff believed that the scores and feedback from their peers had informed these students what actions should be taken to address their shortfalls. Staff observed that overall student's engagement in the workshop continued to be positive.

In previous years the programme used the probation method to address students who either disengage or contribute to the minimal, administrator would need to move students from one group to another or sometimes dismantle groups because of not enough people left in the group. With the introduction of IPAC in 2018, the programme administrator reported that no such arrangement was required at all.

Although the completion rate of the second round of the IPAC summative assessment is lower at 70%, the scores and feedback on the individual who did not take part were consistent to the first round. The cause of the lower level of participation was due to the timing of the assessment: it was launched after the final assessment when students started their summer holiday break.

Due to the introduction of the IPAC as a form of peer assessment, it is not possible to compare the assessment grades between 2017 and 2018 whether students achieve better grades when the programme incorporates peer assessment method. For the purpose of this paper, data are drawn from the teaching log in 2017 and 2018 to compare the total number of staff report about student engagement. A sample of comments from students completed in the IPAC are also used to indicate the level of their team work experience and comments from two internal evaluation reports.

In 2017 (using probation method) a total of 81 entries were reported about student's disengagement or problems of student working in a team. In 2018 (using IPAC only) there were only 8 such reports filed to the teaching team.

Most of the students used the feedback to comment on their peers constructively and there were a high percentage of comments expressing satisfied with their group contributions, such as:

“Good teamwork and communication. Contributed a lot to the project.”

“Her point of view to the project was beneficial as she did not see it as an engineer like the rest of us. Looking at the project through a management point of view helped us find the best solution in terms of feasibility. She was a great team member to work with.”

“Fantastic leadership and managerial skills. Contributed greatly to the team's success and was the driving force behind explaining our ideas to other people.”

“Took leadership of the team and was able to provide a very good understanding from a chemical engineering background, punctual and on time to each session and meeting, often having to remind others to make it on time. Worked diligently to address any concerns the team might have had throughout the project and communicated well throughout.”

“He played a key role to the group's success. His strong technical skills allowed us to come up with a solid engineering solution. He notably designed a 3D model for the presentation and inspected all technical specifications to answer questions efficiently. Even though he is reserved, he also demonstrated excellent team-working skills, in particular respect, careful listening and constructive attitude.”

The positive use of IPAC is also confirmed by two internal evaluation reports.

HtCtW 2018 Report (2108) stated that staff believed the use of IPAC contributed to a very positive approach on the part of most students. When it was first explained at the very start of the programme, it seemed to add its motivational effectiveness.

How to Change the World 2018: Summary of evidence from stakeholder interviews (2018) pointed out that despite a progressively improving trajectory with each delivery of the activity, student engagement at the start of HtCtW continued to be low, driven by the timing of the activity, immediately after the end-of-year exams. During the initial few days of the activity –while participants were struggling to adjust to their new teams and grappling with the challenge of addressing unfamiliar open-ended problems –many continued to demonstrate low engagement levels. However, interview feedback consistently pointed to a significant increase in engagement as participants progressed towards the end of the first week of the activity, which then continued to rise throughout the second week. These improved levels of student engagement were often manifested in an increased likelihood of participants’ citing the high-quality contributions of their teammates: *“our group worked well. They had the right mindset and put the hours in”*. Indeed, most participants consulted for this review reported that they were dedicating four–eight hours per day to unscheduled, independent work on their project, either individually or as a team. High levels of engagement were also evident in the observations of the supervised team sessions, where, in the words of one PGTA, “the students are focused on their problems, that’s been the atmosphere [in the room], most of them are really thinking about the feedback from [the challenge partners]and getting on with it.” The author of the report concluded that the introduction of IPAC peer assessment, providing reassurance that participants would *“get what they deserve rather than a group mark”* in the activity’s assessment.

3 CONCLUSION

The introduction of the IPAC to HtCtW Programme has been very positive overall. Staff agreed that IPAC promotes a more positive approach to motivate student participate in team work than the probation method. While the probation method only threatens students to be penalised for disengagement with a zero mark, IPAC gives a fairer marks for individual contribution by rewarding good contribution and giving lower marks for less contribution. As a result, students use the IPAC to self-regulate their teams.

IPAC also allows staff to understand the group dynamic during the course of the team work and provides them scopes to try to address the issues.

A key concern of adopting IPAC is the ability of performing the technical tasks with the software. To generate the IPAC data, students need to complete the IPAC questionnaire in an identical order as their team list. The operator of the software is also required to prepare the group file consisting of student data from Moodle in a specific file format that matches the data file from the IPAC questionnaire. The software will fail to generate the data if any of the requirements are not met. The technical aspect of operating the software may put some staff off.

Despite some students gave their peers same score and same comment across each of the assessed areas, the software were not able adjust their IPAC score accordingly.

Although the feedback from both students and staff cannot conclusively confirm the introduction of the IPAC had assisted them to achieve higher learning level, the feedback from the peer assessment had shown that they better understood the required proficiency to achieve the expected learning outcomes. The significant reduction of reported incidents concerning student engagement from staff has shown the peer assessment method had an impact on the overall student engagement. To further explore the effectiveness of peer assessment in problem-based learning, more work is needed to minimise a cooperative and non-judgemental atmosphere within a group.

Some students also demonstrated poor quality of feedback to their peers and often very superficial. More support to equip students with the skills to provide feedback and more opportunities for them to practise can address this issue. Lastly a structured peer assessment evaluation will generate more data to better inform further practices.

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